

Working Cultural Values and Social Capital The Influence on Entrepreneurial Behavior of Sonder Community in Indonesia

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Abstract:- This study aims to determine the entrepreneurial behavior of the entrepreneur community from Sonder. The "Sonder people" community was chosen as the object and subject of this study because the Sonder people were given the nickname "Minahasa Chinese". This is based on Minahasa history which states that the Sonder people have the ability to do business on a par with traders from China. The estimated population of Sonder people entrepreneurs is 250 people spread across Manado City, Tomohon City and in Sonder District. The sample was determined as many as 135 entrepreneurs (54%) from the total population. The analytical tool used to test the data and prove the hypothesis is the SEM-PLS program. The results of the study show that partially there is no effect of work values on social capital, but work values do influence entrepreneurial behavior. Work culture partially influences social capital and entrepreneurial behavior. Furthermore, partially social capital has an influence on entrepreneurial behavior. Then, social capital is not a moderating factor between work values and entrepreneurial behavior, but social capital is a moderating factor of work culture on entrepreneurial behavior. In the end there is a simultaneous influence between work values, work culture and social capital on entrepreneurial behavior. The novelty of this research lies in the variety of types of business that entrepreneurs are currently doing, compared to the types of businesses that were carried out by entrepreneurs in the past. The implications of this study indicate that because there has been a change in the work values of Sonder people entrepreneurs so that they do not contribute to social capital, it is deemed necessary to explore the work values of Sonder's "old people" in the past to become a driving force. entrepreneurship for young people Sonder. The limitations of this study lie in the use of quantitative approaches and analytical tools. To complement this research in order to obtain more comprehensive results, it is necessary to study and analyze qualitatively by involving informants from entrepreneurs before the 2000s.

Keywords:- Values, Work Culture, Social Capital, Entrepreneurial Behavior.

I. INTRODUCTION

People who choose to become entrepreneurs need basic capital in the form of qualified work values and work culture. The meaning of entrepreneurship itself is a struggle to do a job. Entrepreneurship requires dynamic and unsustainable changes in circumstances and is initiated by a unique human will (Bygrave, 1993); have unique personality characteristics and abilities (Sahut & Peris-Ortiz, 2014). Entrepreneurial activity has an impact on various sectors and all levels of society, because it is related to innovation, competitiveness, productivity, job creation, and the formation of new industries (Kuratko et al., 2015). In general, humans have values that form the basis of living life. This includes values in choosing and determining the work to be occupied. Values are indicators of individual decisions and actions (Rokeach, 1973), and as expectations for future career choices (de Hauw & de Vos, 2010). Because of this, work values are seen as expressions of basic values in the work environment (Ros et al., 1999).

Work values are one of the factors that can direct humans when trying to achieve life goals, including when joining an organization. These factors can be differences in age and generation (Hansen & Leuty, 2012); age and gender (Parry & Urwin, 2011); generational and career differences (Kuron et al., 2015); job satisfaction, organizational commitment and desire to leave the organization (Cennamo & Gardner, 2008). It can also have an impact on the organization in the future (Gehman et al., 2013).

Work culture is one of the factors that has an impact on the success or failure of individuals in doing work. In work life, individuals who have a good work culture tend to be successful in work activities. Culture is seen as a shared knowledge structure that is interpreted by individuals and can stimulate work activities (Erez & Earley, 2011). Work culture is how to interact informally and formally in group interactions (Green, 2005).

Social capital is a form of asset owned by the community in carrying out daily life activities. In reality, social capital has a broad scope and scope according to the potential that exists in individuals who crystallize in the norms of the community and society at large. Social capital is a broad term that contains social networks and norms that generate mutual understanding, trust and reciprocity, which sustain cooperation and collective action for mutual benefit, and create the foundation for economic prosperity (Dinda, 2008). Some experts argue that social networks are the foundation of social capital which simultaneously encapsulates individuals and social structures, thus functioning as important conceptual links between action and structural constraints, between micro and macro level analyzes, and between relational and collective dynamic processes (Cook, 2017).

A. Work Values

Every human being has a social background with norms that shape work values. When someone chooses a profession and a job, it must be based on work values that can guide and encourage work success. In countries that adopt a liberal economy, the values of the Protestant work ethic are one of the drivers of success at work. The results of this study show a correlation between contemporary work values and the Protestant work ethic. That the Protestant work ethic is related to entrepreneurship and masculine values both in the cultural context and with feminine values in the Turkish context. There is also a link between the role of religiosity in PWE indicating that highly religious participants reported higher PWE scores than less religious participants regardless of culture (Karakitapoğlu Aygün et al., 2008). Empirical evidence shows that there are differences in work values between generations (Parry & Urwin, 2011) and work values have differences between generations in the hotel industry in the United States (Chen & Choi, 2008). Generational differences significantly have different views and attitudes towards authority and work values perspective (Gursoy et al., 2008). Furthermore, men and women are attracted to entrepreneurial careers based on work values. gender influences work value relationships and certain career intentions, such as entrepreneurship (Hirschi & Fischer, 2013).

B. Work Culture

Culture is seen as a shared knowledge structure that produces something based on the interpretation of a stimulus (Erez & Earley, 2011). Work is the result of human work and initiative. In the cultural context, work is a reflection of the results of the taste and intention embodied in certain products. For example, the cultural works of artists, designers, and media workers have become the focus of attention as a 'creative class' of entrepreneurs (Gill & Pratt, 2008). Culture is proxied by past female labor force participation with values related to economic and institutional conditions, and related to women's role for the state (Fernandez & Fogli, 2009). Aspects of work culture can increase job satisfaction and increase family welfare (Clark, 2001). Viewed from the aspect of regional culture, it indirectly influences entrepreneurial capital, and people in some areas are more pro-entrepreneurship because basically they have a high

intention to become entrepreneurs which is influenced by their cultural characteristics (Jaén & Liñán, 2013).

C. Social Capital

French sociologist Pierre Bourdieu defines social capital as "the amount of resources, actual or virtual, acquired by individuals or groups based on long-standing network ownership associated with institutions that know each other on the basis of recognition" (Whiteley, 2015). Social capital can simply be interpreted as a set of informal values or shared norms among group members that enable them to cooperate with one another (Durlauf, 2002). Social capital is the glue that binds society together and without entrepreneurship there can be no economic growth or human well-being (Jordan & Jordan, 2012).

There are several things related to social capital: (1) social capital facilitates the creation of new intellectual capital; (2) organization, as an institutional arrangement, is conducive to the development of high levels of social capital; and (3) having more intensive social capital, within certain limits makes the company have an advantage in the market to create shared intellectual capital (Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 2009). There are three forms of social capital, namely: obligations and expectations, information channels, and social norms (Coleman, 2009). The economic literature includes social capital to explain regional disparities. The economic development of a country depends on the impact of social capital which includes socio-culture, norms and regulations that encourage economic reforms and development activities (Dinda, 2014). From the aspect of the sociological discipline, there are four sources of social capital which emphasize their role in social control, family support, and extra-familial benefits and networks (Portes, 2009). Social capital helps entrepreneurs to overcome resource constraints (Bauernschuster et al., 2010).

D. Entrepreneurial Behavior

The field of entrepreneurship has developed in somewhat disjointed ways, and entrepreneurship has developed as a business discipline by borrowing and adapting various theories and conceptualizations from fields such as sociology, psychology, anthropology, marketing, management, finance, organizational behavior, and engineering. Kuratko et al., 2015). Entrepreneurial success requires the integration of values from each culture, where the satisfaction of giving is correlated with the social benefits of rigorous problem solving (Dees, 2012). Attitudes toward sustainability and perceived entrepreneurial desire increase entrepreneurial intentions that are oriented toward sustainability (Vuorio et al., 2018).

Entrepreneurial capital can contribute to a more entrepreneurial work force with work values aligned with needs, so that it becomes one of the company's strategic resources (Jaén & Liñán, 2013). Four specific values are believed to be important for motivating entrepreneurial behavior, namely independence, creativity, ambition, and courage (Kirkley, 2016). However, there are research results confirming the relationship between values and intentions

that can support the view that values can direct job choices in entrepreneurship (Tipu & Ryan, 2016).

The results of the study revealed that a person's success is not only determined by knowledge and technical skills (hard skills), but by self-management skills and other people (soft skills). This research reveals, success is only determined by approximately 20% by hard skills and the remaining 80% by soft skills. Interpersonal skills are also possessed by an entrepreneur to perform creative tasks. Creativity is an essential element, the existence and development of a business. In Indonesia alone, the diversity of businesses and the number of entrepreneurs is incalculable compared to the United States or in other countries. Around 0.18% are entrepreneurs, therefore it is necessary to develop soft skills in order to foster an entrepreneurial spirit. (Bygrave, 2010). Comparing German entrepreneurs two decades after reunification reveals that children whose parents were entrepreneurs faced much resistance in socialist East Germany, because entrepreneurial behavior in East Germany was far more likely to run their own businesses than entrepreneurs whose parents had entrepreneurs who do not experience challenges like those in East Germany (Wyrwich, 2015). Differences in labor market outcomes and the value of work of immigrants from the Maghreb versus Southern Europe are, statistically speaking, fully explained by differences in levels of entrepreneurial capital (Senik & Verdier, 2011). Perseverance and market insight contribute positively to staying active as an entrepreneur (Kyndt & Baert, 2015). However, entrepreneurial intentions are determined by cognitive and social factors rather than psychological traits (Cantner et al., 2017). Entrepreneurial behavior, shown by innovation, proactivity, and risk taking items, is the highest construct (de Jong et al., 2015).

II. PAPER OBJECTIVE

This study aims to determine the effect of the variables partially and simultaneously work values, work culture, social capital and entrepreneurial behavior.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research is survey research using a quantitative approach. The form of research is explanatory research to explain the relationship between variables (correlational research), with the aim of examining the causal relationship between work values, work culture and capital and entrepreneurial behavior of Sonder people business actors. The data analysis technique uses the Structural Equation Mode (SEM)-PLS model with the aim of knowing the interaction between the variables of work values, work culture, social capital and entrepreneurial behavior. The selection of the SEM-PLS analysis tool as a data analysis method is based on several reasons such as: (1) The model is structural, in which there is a tiered causality relationship, namely from the variables of work values, work culture to social capital and entrepreneurial behavior; (2) The variables in this study are unobservable with measurements based on several indicators; (3) SEM-PLS provides a direct method

related to multiple relationships simultaneously while providing statistical analysis efficiency.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Proof of Hypothesis 1: work values affect social capital.

The first hypothesis tests whether there is an effect of work values on social capital.

The null hypothesis (H0) and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) are arranged as follows:

(H0): There is no effect of work values on social capital

(Ha): There is an influence of work values on social capital

Table 1 shows the results of the Original Sample = 0.150, T Statistics = 1.279 and the significance level (P values) = 0.202. Because the significance level of 0.202 means greater than 0.05 as a predetermined level of significance, then Ho can be accepted and Ha rejected. This shows that the effect of work values on social capital is positive but not significant. Thus H1 in this study is rejected, meaning that work values cannot increase social capital.

B. Proof of Hypothesis 2: work values influence entrepreneurial behavior.

The second hypothesis tests whether there is an effect of work values on entrepreneurial behavior.

The null hypothesis (H0) and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) are arranged as follows:

(H0): There is no effect of work values on entrepreneurial behavior.

(Ha): There is an influence of work values on entrepreneurial behavior

Table 1 shows the results of the Original Sample = 0.319, T Statistics = 2.859 and the significance level (P values) = 0.004. Because a significance level of 0.004 means less than 0.05 as a predetermined significance level, then Ho can be rejected and Ha accepted. This shows that the influence of work values on entrepreneurial behavior is significantly positive. Thus H2 in this study is accepted. This means that work values can increase entrepreneurial behavior.

C. Proof of Hypothesis 3: work culture influences social capital

The fourth hypothesis tests whether there is an effect of work culture on social capital.

The null hypothesis (H0) and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) are arranged as follows:

(H0): There is no effect of work culture on social capital.

(Ha): There is an influence of work culture on social capital

Table 1 shows the results of the Original Sample = 0.629, T Statistics = 5.744 and the significance level (P values) = 0.000. Because a significance level of 0.000 means less than 0.05 as a predetermined significance level, then Ho can be rejected and Ha accepted. This shows that the effect of work culture on social capital is significant positive. Thus H3 in this study is accepted, meaning that work culture can increase social capital.

D. Proof of Hypothesis 4: work culture influences entrepreneurial behavior.

The fifth hypothesis tests whether there is an influence of work culture on entrepreneurial behavior.

The null hypothesis (H0) and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) are arranged as follows:

(H0): There is no influence of work culture on entrepreneurial behavior.

(Ha): There is an influence of work culture on entrepreneurial behavior

Table 1 shows the results of the Original Sample = 0.286, T Statistics = 2.690 and the significance level (P values) = 0.007. Because a significance level of 0.007 means less than 0.05 as a predetermined significance level, then Ho can be rejected and Ha accepted. This shows that the influence of work culture on entrepreneurial behavior is significantly positive. Thus H4 in this study is accepted. This means that work culture can increase entrepreneurial behavior.

E. Proof of Hypothesis 5: social capital influences entrepreneurial behavior

The sixth hypothesis tests whether there is an effect of social capital on entrepreneurial behavior.

The null hypothesis (H0) and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) are arranged as follows:

(H0): There is no effect of social capital on entrepreneurial behavior.

(Ha): There is an influence of social capital on entrepreneurial behavior.

Table 1 shows the results of the Original Sample = 0.262, T Statistics = 2.806 and the significance level (P values) = 0.005. Because a significance level of 0.005 means less than 0.05 as a predetermined significance level, then Ho can be rejected and Ha accepted. This shows that the influence of social capital on entrepreneurial behavior is significantly positive. Thus H5 in this study is accepted, meaning that social capital can increase entrepreneurial behavior.

F. Proof of Hypothesis 6: work values influence entrepreneurial behavior through social capital

The third hypothesis tests whether there is an effect of work values on entrepreneurial behavior through social capital.

The null hypothesis (H0) and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) are arranged as follows:

(H0): There is no effect of work values on entrepreneurial behavior through social capital.

(Ha): There is an influence of work values on entrepreneurial behavior through social capital

Table 1 shows the results of the Original Sample = 0.039, T Statistics = 1.068 and the significance level (P values) = 0.289. Because the significance level of 0.289 means greater than 0.05 as a predetermined level of

significance, then Ho can be accepted and Ha rejected. This shows that the effect of work values on entrepreneurial behavior through social capital is positive but not significant. Thus H6 in this study was rejected. This means that the influence of work values on entrepreneurial behavior through social capital cannot increase entrepreneurial behavior.

Table 1. Path Coefficients

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values	Conclusion
Work Values -> Social Capital	0.150	0.151	0.117	1.279	0.202	Not Significant
Work Values -> Entrepreneurial Behaviour	0.319	0.314	0.111	2.859	0.004	Significant
Work Culture -> Social Capital	0.629	0.632	0.110	5.744	0.000	Significant
Work Culture -> Entrepreneurial Behaviour	0.286	0.294	0.106	2.690	0.007	Significant
Social Capital -> Entrepreneurial Behaviour	0.262	0.260	0.093	2.806	0.005	Significant

Source: attachment

G. Proof of Hypothesis 7: work culture influences entrepreneurial behavior through social capital.

The seventh hypothesis tests whether there is an influence of work culture on entrepreneurial behavior through social capital.

The null hypothesis (H0) and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) are arranged as follows:

(H0): There is no influence of work culture on entrepreneurial behavior through social capital.

(Ha): There is an influence of work culture on entrepreneurial behavior through social capital.

Table 2 shows the results of the Original Sample = 0.165, T Statistics = 2.623 and the significance level (P values) = 0.009. Because a significance level of 0.009 means less than 0.05 as a predetermined significance level, then Ho can be rejected and Ha accepted. This shows that work culture has a significant positive effect on entrepreneurial behavior through social capital. Thus H7 in this study is accepted, meaning that work culture through social capital can increase entrepreneurial behavior.

Table 2. Total Indirect Effects

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values	Conclusion
Work Culture -> Social Capital						
Work Culture -> Perilaku Kewirausahaan	0.165	0.163	0.063	2.623	0.009	Significant
Modal Sosial -> Entrepreneurial Behaviour						
Nilai-Nilai Kerja -> Modal Sosial						
Work Values -> Entrepreneurial Behaviour	0.039	0.040	0.037	1.068	0.286	Not Significant

Source: Attached

Based on testing the model variables in the study are grouped into two groups, namely the dependent variable and the independent variable. The independent variables are work values, work culture and social capital. The dependent variable is entrepreneurial behavior. The model is said to be good when the theoretical development of the hypothetical model is supported by empirical data. Testing the results of the PLS analysis of the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable in full can be seen in Table 3.

Tabel 3. Kriteria Kualitas

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Modal Sosial	0.577	0.571
Perilaku Kewirausahaan	0.631	0.623

Source: Attached

Based on Table 3, it can be seen that the R Square Adjusted value is 0.571 for the social capital construct. This shows that work values, work culture that influence social capital variables are 57.1%, the remaining 42.9% are influenced by other variables. This shows that the research model is quite good. It can also be seen that the value of R Square Adjusted is 0.623 for the construct of entrepreneurial behavior. This shows that work values, work culture and social capital together influence the entrepreneurial behavior variable by 62.3%, the remaining 37.7% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

V. DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the analysis of the six hypotheses, it was found that four hypotheses were accepted and two hypotheses were rejected. The following description discusses the findings of the hypotheses tested in this study.

A. The Effect of Work Values on Social Capital

The results of the analysis on the first hypothesis to test whether there is an effect of work values on social capital, it is found that there is no effect of work values on social capital. This means that the work values of business actors do not affect their social capital. Thus, this research is not in line with research findings which state that if the analogy is "sufficient work experience" as "work values" and "strong social network" as "social capital" for unemployed and reemployed parents (Gayen et al., 2019) then work values have an impact on social capital. Opinions that work values act as basic principles that guide individual behavior are related to work, and there is a moderate influence from the general socio-cultural context such as generational differences and peer influence have an impact on the work values of young people (Cemalcilar et al., 2018).

An idea developed by Allport in 1961 who argued that personal life philosophy related to values is a core feature of personality which implies the direction of motivation, future goals, and current choices (Oles & Hermans, 2010). Referring to the notion of value as a belief that causes individuals to act based on their preferences (Allport, 1961) in (Malinowska & Tokarz, 2019), then from this opinion if people perceive experience in doing the profession as entrepreneurs from Sonder people that the majority have independent businesses

in the form of clove cultivation and trading. This is the trigger for the birth of social capital which is the fundamental of the community to fight for the life of families and community groups for joint economic progress. And currently the millennial generation is the successor to the entrepreneurial values of the baby boomers generation of Sonder people business people. Because there are similarities in values between parents and children in carrying out work, especially regarding entrepreneurship (Laspita et al., 2012). Also peers can form values that reinforce social capital through a process of competition thereby giving legitimacy to social groups (Belliveau et al., 1996).

Work values determine the general motivation to work and what type of work we seek (Gesthuizen et al., 2019). Studies on work values are discussed and discussed in several social science disciplines such as sociology, psychology, economics, and political science so as to produce various understandings because they are analyzed from various variations of work values. (Cemalcilar et al., 2018). A study examining the value of work with representatives of the Baby Boomers, Generation X, and Generation Y generations. The value of leisure has steadily increased over the generations and the centrality of work has decreased. Extrinsic values such as status and money peak with GenX but are still higher among Gen Y than among Boomers. Contrary to popular press reports, Gen Y dislikes the value of altruistic work such as providing assistance and social value compared to previous generations. Social values such as friendship and intrinsic values such as interesting and result-oriented jobs are rated lower by Gen Y than by baby boomers (Twenge et al., 2010). There are differences in the work values of different generational groups and individuals, such as Generations X and Y, have different work values than individuals from the Baby Boomers generation (Leuty & Hansen, 2011).

In fact, the majority of entrepreneurs from Sonder are in the X and Y generations, namely 32.60% are aged 45 to 54 years and 21.50% are aged 55 to 64 years or a total of 54.10% were born in the late 1950s. and the 1960s. Business actors belonging to the X and Y generation category grew and developed in the era of relatively good economic conditions in the Sonder community, because the yield of clove plantations in the 1970s and 1980s was at a high price. This statement is supported by the opinion which states that "the new wealth mainly comes from clove production, which brought wealth to most producers and traders, especially in the 1970s and early 1980s (Maria J. Schouten, 2004). In contrast to the baby boomers generation and previous generations who grew up in a quite difficult era due to experiencing famine due to the first world war, second world war and the permesta war. They have strong work values and work ethic with the aim of changing their lives for a better economy and a more prosperous family.

B. Effect of Work Values on Entrepreneurial Behavior

The results of the analysis of the effect of work values on entrepreneurial behavior show a positive and significant value. Thus, Sonder entrepreneurs interpret work values to increase their entrepreneurial behavior. This is in line with empirical evidence which states that work values are

positively correlated with entrepreneurship (Terrell & Troilo, 2010). Then, work values in terms of gender aspects make them interested in entrepreneurial careers. Therefore, work values influence certain career intentions such as entrepreneurship (Hirschi & Fischer, 2013). The intention to act as an entrepreneur is determined by cognitive and social factors rather than psychological characteristics (Cantner et al., 2017). Work values that are implemented on family values have shaped entrepreneurial behavior which is very important for sustainable entrepreneurial growth over a long period of time (Raitis et al., 2021). Social norms have a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurial intentions (Ephrem et al., 2019). Personal values related to individual desires in work and career have empirical evidence related to the desire to be entrepreneurial (Sánchez, 2021). Personal characteristics, values and identity are recognized as important factors driving the entrepreneurial behavior of small firms in Finland (Soininen et al., 2015). Work values such as comfort and security have a significant negative effect on entrepreneurial attitudes, but work values such as "competence and growth" and "status and independence" have a significant positive impact on entrepreneurial attitudes (Haikun & Moon, 2019).

Social factors can be partially interpreted as containing social values such as a work ethic which is a lever to carry out communal activities as business actors in order to meet the economic needs of the family and social obligations related to the communal economy. The glorious era of entrepreneurial Sonder people was supported by prosperity with success in the agricultural sector, especially clove farming in the 1960s to 1980s where the Sonder plantation area was one of the largest clove producers in Minahasa district (Schouten, 2019). In the context of work values that are spirituality in nature, there is research which finds that spiritual entrepreneurs refer to people who run their business according to ethical and religious values, where they interpret their work as worship, honesty, and gratitude in addition to good entrepreneurial behavior. such as innovation, proactivity, competitive aggressiveness, risk taking, autonomy (Nursiani et al., 2019). The behavior of women entrepreneurs or women entrepreneurs becomes more independent due to changes in work values or cultural norms and values (Basit et al., 2020). Basically the value system of entrepreneurs and their entrepreneurial behavior has an impact on economic efficiency and, ultimately on the overall welfare of society (Korneiko, 2017).

From the various work values that are believed by business actors as found from various studies originating from several countries, basically they have an impact and influence on entrepreneurial behavior. This can be interpreted that individual work values are part of the larger values of a community and country and can change along with the influence of global values that affect almost all human life. Because of this, the values of the entrepreneur from Sonder have not been spared from temporary global changes. The massive information consumed by the Sonder people through mainstream media such as television and print media as well as social media has consciously or unwittingly changed their

work values which are no longer the same as those of their parents and elders in the past.

C. Work Values Influence Entrepreneurial Behavior Through Social Capital

The effect of work values on entrepreneurial behavior through capital has no significant effect. This means that work values do not affect entrepreneurial behavior through social capital. Thus, this study is not in accordance with research findings which state that social capital which is manifested in the form of psychological capital positively mediates the relationship between work values or social norms and entrepreneurial behavior and increases intention to do business (Ephrem et al., 2019). Social capital is significantly related to entrepreneurial intentions, so they have attitudes and behaviors to become entrepreneurs (Malebana, 2019). Cross-ethnic social capital creates benefits for business actors, and business relationships create social values in the form of friendship and trust that shape entrepreneurial behavior (Kopren & Westlund, 2021). Entrepreneurs are the lifeblood of small businesses, the structural dimension of social capital is most important in influencing behavior to seek entrepreneurial opportunities (David Jawahar & Nigama, 2011). Social capital assumes how entrepreneurs behave. With special characteristics of entrepreneurial behavior such as building trust, it becomes the basic capital for business actors to innovate (Iivonen et al., 2011).

There is research which finds that experience, mentoring, and the social environment/work values are factors that can support the tendency of people to become entrepreneurs and survey results reveal that two-thirds of individuals in 38 countries become entrepreneurs because they are created and not born (Robbins & Judge, 2017). This means that the value contains the elements of truth and goodness that the individual wants. Also, everyone has a value system that has a relatively different hierarchy of interests. Therefore, changing values becomes an inseparable part of the interaction process of each person with the environment and the period or generation in question lives. Entrepreneurs from Sonder are currently born, grow and develop in an era full of changing values. For example, the Sonder community in the past was full of social interactions that upheld mutual cooperation behavior for various social activities. Obedience in following various social norms with values of kindness and honesty becomes something that is spontaneous and sincere. However, currently the principled values of gotong royong have shifted to forms that tend to be transactional. Economic considerations with transactions of a financial nature have become a consideration for most Sonder people. A real form of change in social values can be seen during rituals and various processions when grief events occur such as "Sumakey", which is a certain celebration with the community (Kimbal & Tangkau, 2021). Gotong-royong, which is a feature of helping grieving families, such as preparing food, at this time generally has to be bailed out by the bereaved family themselves.

D. *The Effect of Work Culture on Social Capital*

The results of the analysis of work culture on social capital show that there is an influence of work culture on social capital. This means that entrepreneurs from Sonder believe that work culture can increase their social capital. Thus the results of this study are in line with research from several previous studies. It is not specific to entrepreneurship research, but to several other social research subjects. Culture has an impact on social capital ((Miquel et al., 2015). Culture can influence the creation and utilization of social capital, and comprehensively can be useful for entrepreneurs, as well as interest groups to better understand the nature, and role of social capital moderated by culture in technology transfer (Grzegorzczak, 2019). Social values in the local traditions of the Minahasa people, namely Mapalus, become social capital in the form of cooperation that grows and develops among Minahasa people such as Pa'ando which is a financial activity in the form of arisan to support their economic activities and to strengthen rural small industries (Kimbal & Tangkau, 2021).

Based on the description of the results of previous research, it can be explained that a work culture based on individual work values that crystallizes in the form of organizational work culture, communal work culture and national work culture is one of the factors that contribute to social capital. Because work culture is a manifestation of the involvement of the workforce which is based on values that have a relationship with macroeconomic conditions. In the context of work culture as an embodiment of attitudes and behavior to produce certain products, it becomes a valuable social capital for the realization of entrepreneurial behavior from Sonder people. From the theoretical aspect, it can be emphasized that culture as a value system that underlies the characteristics of certain groups or societies has shaped the development of certain personality traits and motivated individuals in society to engage in behaviors that may not be seen in other societies (Mueller & Thomas, 2001) such as For example, entrepreneurial behavior.

E. *The Influence of Work Culture on Entrepreneurial Behavior*

Working culture statistically in this study proved to influence entrepreneurial behavior. This shows that the work culture of the entrepreneurs from Sonder contributes to their entrepreneurial behavior. Thus this research is in line with several previous studies such as the following where culture is related to entrepreneurial behavior, but empirically shows that there is no ideal context for one country. This is because in order to achieve the results expected by the community, it is necessary to align the model that best suits their own culture (Torres & Augusto, 2019). Individual cultural differences have an influence on entrepreneurial behavior in the Cape Republic region (García-Cabrera & García-Soto, 2008). Hofstede's research approach to national cultures found that some national cultures are more conducive to entrepreneurship, and cultures can condition entrepreneurial potential with differences across national and regional boundaries. That a national culture that supports "ceteris paribus" can increase the entrepreneurial potential of a country (Mueller & Thomas, 2001).

The work culture that is formed from values inherited from parents, environment and situations has shaped life choices in meeting the needs of life and family economic growth. Sonder people who choose the profession as entrepreneurs have set life goals that are in accordance with the values they believe in for the future life and economic growth of the family. The following expert opinion states that an individual's choice to become or be forced to become an entrepreneur will be based on the individual's past activities, present situation and future aspirations. This choice will be influenced by the surrounding environment and culture, with processes seen as specific changes in an individual's living space (Kjellman & Ehrsten, 2005).

F. *The Effect of Social Capital on Entrepreneurial Behavior*

Social capital based on the results of hypothesis testing has an influence on entrepreneurial behavior. Thus, social capital can increase the entrepreneurial behavior of Sonder people who choose the profession as entrepreneurs. Because of this, several previous studies support this research, with findings stating that entrepreneurial behavior is influenced by social and environmental factors (Diale et al., 2021). Social and environmental factors as social capital are a means of forming intentions to determine the work to be carried out in the future. Communities that exist in the Sonder community generally form an intention to become an entrepreneur because in the past it was a relatively poor area (Schouten, 1994), so they worked hard to get out of poverty by choosing the profession of being an entrepreneur. Social capital has been assumed to be a valuable non-financial resource because through individual, social and organizational connections one can access information and resources to gain profit through entrepreneurial behavior (Zhang et al., 2021).

Findings that are relevant to the socio-economic life of the Minahasa people that social capital has an impact on livestock traders' business activities when transactions occur in the form of sharing product price information, livestock that meet the requirements, low-cost transactions, and access to financial resources in local markets (Kimbal, 2015). Entrepreneurship is important for economic growth, through its role in providing employment. The development of entrepreneurship courses and education as an effort to meet the demands of entrepreneurs in the market, makes a direct contribution to increasing entrepreneurial intentions (Ephrem et al., 2019). Factually, the Sonder community is built with social capital that comes from senior figures who have a strong work ethic in building the family economy. The ability to carry out social mobility by seeking work "outside the village" both as a farmer and as a trader has shaped entrepreneurial behavior. The following expression is historical evidence that around 1920 the Sonder people began to become itinerant traders, and because their expertise in trading had gained the trust of Chinese traders in Manado, the Sonder people were referred to as "Minahasa Chinese" (Wenas, 2007). Thus, the social capital possessed by the Sonder people as traders in the past, continues to be passed on to their children and grandchildren until now as entrepreneurs.

G. The Influence of Work Culture on Entrepreneurial Behavior Through Social Capital

The results of the analysis of the influence of work culture on entrepreneurial behavior through social capital found that there was a positive and significant effect. This shows that Sonder people entrepreneurs believe that work culture through social capital has an impact on entrepreneurial behavior. Thus, this research is in line with the results of previous research, such as the results of the following research which state that culture can affect social capital for external stakeholders in technology transfer for industry players and government policies, but also internal relations and management style in the form of organizational culture (Grzegorzcyk, 2019). In the macro context, institutions in the form of companies cannot be separated from cultural influences. Institutions and culture interact and develop in complementary ways (Azis, 2019). Therefore, the implementation of a more tangible culture such as work culture has an impact on institutions in a tangible form such as business entities in the form of MSMEs that are born from the entrepreneurial behavior of certain communities.

Entrepreneurial behavior is not born from a vacuum, but from human creations and realistic thoughts to create certain artifacts for human needs. Because of that there is an opinion that says something like this "in an anthropological perspective, culture and the creative economy have a correlation, both of which come from unlimited human ideas. Through ideas, both find their foundation in turning social capital into economic capital and vice versa (Ramdhani, 2020). To make positive social changes, efforts to foster an entrepreneurial culture are a means of fostering social resilience. Socio-economic development with entrepreneurial actions for communities is influenced by the geographical and socio-economic characteristics of each community (Hodge et al., 2021). The Sonder people are in fact a growing community with an entrepreneurial spirit. This is evidenced by the long journey since before 1900 to carry out a traveling business using carts or "horse wheels" (Wenas, 2007). Thus, the work culture has crystallized in the form of social capital for the Sonder community to carry out entrepreneurial activities since a long time ago.

H. Relationship between Work Values, Work Culture, Social Capital and Entrepreneurial Behavior

Based on the results of the overall analysis of the independent variables, it was found that work values and social capital together had an influence on social capital by 57%. Then, 43% of social capital is influenced by other variables not examined in this study. Meanwhile, entrepreneurial behavior is jointly influenced by work values, work culture and social capital by 62%. Other variables not examined contributed to the influence on entrepreneurial behavior by 38%.

Empirically the results of this study are in line with several previous studies such as the relationship between work values, work culture, social capital and entrepreneurial behavior. Economic achievements in various countries were initially based on entrepreneur behavior before arriving at entrepreneurial behavior (McClelland & McClelland, 2013). Work values have a relationship with certain career

intentions, including as an entrepreneur (Hirschi & Fischer, 2013). Work values are positively related to entrepreneurship (Terrell & Troilo, 2010). Work culture has the potential to increase the performance of entrepreneurial culture (Sinha et al., 2010). Social capital is important in understanding entrepreneurial behavior (De Carolis & Saporito, 2006). Social capital has an impact on entrepreneurship (Bauernschuster et al., 2010). Thus, the results of this study contribute to entrepreneurship theory, and as one of the empirical foundations for further entrepreneurship research in the future.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion in the previous section of this paper, it can be concluded as follows:

- The work values believed by the entrepreneurs of the Sonder people cannot actually increase social capital as the basis for carrying out business activities.
- Work values can increase the entrepreneurial behavior of Sonder people in their business activities.
- It turns out that social capital has not been able to become an intermediary factor that contributes between work values and an increase in entrepreneurial behavior.
- The entrepreneurial work culture of the Sonder people has an impact on strengthening social capital for their work activities.
- The work culture has in fact had an impact on the entrepreneurial behavior of the Sonder people in running their businesses.
- The social capital that has been inherited from the Sonder people's predecessors is one of the factors that strengthens the formation of their entrepreneurial behavior in business activities.
- It turns out that the work culture has contributed to the entrepreneurial behavior of the Sonder people through the social capital that has existed in their community for generations.

The combination of work values, work culture and social capital actually contributed significantly to the entrepreneurial behavior of the Sonder people when they developed various types of businesses.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings in this study, it is necessary to provide input as follows:

- Because the flow of globalization has eroded the various aspects of the life of the majority of people in this world, including the work values of the Sonder people, it is necessary to make efforts to exhume the work values of the old people as an inheritance to strengthen social capital.
- Given that work values make a significant contribution to entrepreneurial behavior, existing work values need to be maintained and even enhanced to provide continuity for the entrepreneurial spirit of the Sonder people.

- Because social capital has not yet become a good intermediary between work values and entrepreneurial behavior, it is necessary to strengthen social capital by digging back into elements of work values that were inherited from Sonder's parents in the past.
- Given that work culture has contributed to the social capital of Sonder people entrepreneurs, the current work culture in the Sonder people entrepreneur community needs to be preserved for the sustainability of their businesses.
- Because the entrepreneurial behavior of the Sonder people is contributed by the social capital they have, the social capital that exists in entrepreneurs needs to be maintained and passed on to the millennial generation of Sonder people entrepreneurs.
- The social capital owned by the Sonder people that has existed for a long time must and must be preserved in order to maintain and continue to improve entrepreneurial behavior in a sustainable manner.
- Because social capital is a good intermediary between work culture and entrepreneurial behavior, Sonder people are obliged to make the existing work culture a reinforcement of social capital to manifest entrepreneurial behavior that promotes business growth and success.
- The real contribution of work values, work culture and social capital to entrepreneurial behavior, then these things should become a philosophical foundation for the sustainability of Sonder people entrepreneurs throughout human civilization.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Azis, I. J. (2019). Economics and culture. *Buletin Ekonomi Moneter Dan Perbankan*. <https://doi.org/10.21098/bemp.v22i1.1035>
- [2]. Basit, A., Hassan, Z., & Sethumadhavan, S. (2020). Entrepreneurial Success: Key Challenges Faced by Malaysian Women Entrepreneurs in 21st Century. *International Journal of Business and Management*. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v15n9p122>
- [3]. Azis, I. J. (2019). Economics and culture. *Buletin Ekonomi Moneter Dan Perbankan*. <https://doi.org/10.21098/bemp.v22i1.1035>
- [4]. Basit, A., Hassan, Z., & Sethumadhavan, S. (2020). Entrepreneurial Success: Key Challenges Faced by Malaysian Women Entrepreneurs in 21st Century. *International Journal of Business and Management*. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v15n9p122>
- [5]. Bauernschuster, S., Falck, O., & Heblich, S. (2010). Social capital access and entrepreneurship. *Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jebo.2010.09.014>
- [6]. Belliveau, M. A., O'Reilly, C. A., & Wade, J. B. (1996). Social capital at the top: Effects of social similarity and status on CEO compensation. *Academy of Management Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2307/257069>
- [7]. Bygrave. (2010). Kontribusi Soft Skill Dalam Menumbuhkan Jiwa Kewirausahaan. *Jurnal Ilmiah Among Makarti*.
- [8]. Bygrave, W. D. (1993). Theory building in the entrepreneurship paradigm. *Journal of Business Venturing*. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0883-9026\(93\)90031-Y](https://doi.org/10.1016/0883-9026(93)90031-Y)
- [9]. Cantner, U., Goethner, M., & Silbereisen, R. K. (2017). Schumpeter's entrepreneur – A rare case. *Journal of Evolutionary Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00191-016-0467-3>
- [10]. Cemalcilar, Z., Secinti, E., & Sumer, N. (2018). Intergenerational Transmission of Work Values: A Meta-Analytic Review. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-018-0858-x>
- [11]. Cennamo, L., & Gardner, D. (2008). Generational differences in work values, outcomes and person-organisation values fit. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02683940810904385>
- [12]. Chen, P. J., & Choi, Y. (2008). Generational differences in work values: A study of hospitality management. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09596110810892182>
- [13]. Clark, S. C. (2001). Work Cultures and Work/Family Balance. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jvbe.2000.1759>
- [14]. Coleman, J. S. (2009). Social capital in the creation of human capital. In *Knowledge and Social Capital*. <https://doi.org/10.1086/228943>
- [15]. Cook, K. (2017). Social Capital: Theory and Research. In *Social Capital: Theory and Research*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315129457>
- [16]. David Jawahar, P., & Nigama, K. (2011). The influence of social capital on entrepreneurial opportunity recognition behaviour. *International Journal of Economics and Management*.
- [17]. De Carolis, D. M., & Saporito, P. (2006). Social capital, cognition, and entrepreneurial opportunities: A theoretical framework. *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6520.2006.00109.x>
- [18]. de Hauw, S., & de Vos, A. (2010). Millennials' career perspective and psychological contract expectations: Does the recession lead to lowered expectations? *Journal of Business and Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-010-9162-9>
- [19]. de Jong, J. P. J., Parker, S. K., Wennekers, S., & Wu, C. H. (2015). Entrepreneurial Behavior in Organizations: Does Job Design Matter? *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/etap.12084>
- [20]. Dees, J. G. (2012). A Tale of Two Cultures: Charity, Problem Solving, and the Future of Social Entrepreneurship. *Journal of Business Ethics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-012-1412-5>
- [21]. Diale, C. D., Kanakana-Katumba, M. G., & Maladzi, R. W. (2021). Environmental entrepreneurship as an innovation catalyst for social change: A systematic review as a basis for future research. *Advances in Science, Technology and Engineering Systems*. <https://doi.org/10.25046/aj060145>

- [22]. Dinda, S. (2008). Social capital in the creation of human capital and economic growth: A productive consumption approach. *Journal of Socio-Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socec.2007.06.014>
- [23]. Dinda, S. (2014). Inclusive growth through creation of human and social capital. *International Journal of Social Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSE-07-2013-0157>
- [24]. Durlauf, S. N. (2002). On the empirics of social capital. *Economic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-0297.00079>
- [25]. Ephrem, A. N., Namatovu, R., & Basalirwa, E. M. (2019). Perceived social norms, psychological capital and entrepreneurial intention among undergraduate students in Bukavu. *Education and Training*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ET-10-2018-0212>
- [26]. Erez, M., & Earley, P. C. (2011). Culture, Self-Identity, and Work. In *Culture, Self-Identity, and Work*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195075809.001.0001>
- [27]. Fernandez, R., & Fogli, A. (2009). Culture: An empirical investigation of beliefs, work, and fertility. *American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics*. <https://doi.org/10.1257/mac.1.1.146>
- [28]. García-Cabrera, A. M., & García-Soto, M. G. (2008). Cultural differences and entrepreneurial behaviour: An intra-country cross-cultural analysis in Cape Verde. *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08985620801912608>
- [29]. Gayen, K., Raeside, R., & McQuaid, R. (2019). Social networks, accessed and mobilised social capital and the employment status of older workers: A case study. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSSP-07-2018-0111>
- [30]. Gehman, J., Treviño, L. K., & Garud, R. (2013). Values Work: A Process Study of the Emergence and Performance of Organizational Values Practices. *Academy of Management Journal*, 56(1), 84–112. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2010.0628>
- [31]. Gesthuizen, M., Kovarek, D., & Rapp, C. (2019). Extrinsic and Intrinsic Work Values: Findings on Equivalence in Different Cultural Contexts. *Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002716219829016>
- [32]. Gill, R., & Pratt, A. (2008). In the Social Factory?: Immaterial Labour, Precariousness and Cultural Work. *Theory, Culture & Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0263276408097794>
- [33]. Green, T. K. (2005). Work culture and discrimination. In *California Law Review*. <https://doi.org/10.15779/Z38DD81>
- [34]. Grzegorzczak, M. (2019). The role of culture-moderated social capital in technology transfer – insights from Asia and America. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2019.01.021>
- [35]. Gursoy, D., Maier, T. A., & Chi, C. G. (2008). Generational differences: An examination of work values and generational gaps in the hospitality workforce. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2007.11.002>
- [36]. Haikun, W., & Moon, J. (2019). The relationship between work values and entrepreneurial attitudes: Implications for the distribution industry. *Journal of Distribution Science*. <https://doi.org/10.15722/jds.17.03.201903.57>
- [37]. Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2010). Multivariate Data Analysis. In *Vectors*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2011.02.019>
- [38]. Hansen, J. I. C., & Leuty, M. E. (2012). Work values across generations. In *Journal of Career Assessment*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10690727111417163>
- [39]. Hirschi, A., & Fischer, S. (2013). Work values as predictors of entrepreneurial career intentions. *Career Development International*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CDI-04-2012-0047>
- [40]. Hodge, P. A., Bon, A. C., Cohen, M., & Turisco, F. (2021). The Quest for Sustainable Communities in Isolated and in Urban Settings. *Journal of Social Entrepreneurship*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19420676.2019.1683876>
- [41]. Iivonen, S., Kyrö, P., Mynttinen, S., Särkkä-Tirkkonen, M., & Kahiluoto, H. (2011). Social capital and entrepreneurial behaviour advancing innovativeness in interaction between small rural entrepreneurs and researchers: A phenomenographic study. *Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1389224X.2011.536348>
- [42]. Jaén, I., & Liñán, F. (2013). Work values in a changing economic environment: The role of entrepreneurial capital. *International Journal of Manpower*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJM-07-2013-0166>
- [43]. Jordan, B., & Jordan, B. (2012). Social capital: the missing link? In *Welfare and well-being Social value in public policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1332/policypress/9781847420800.003.0005>
- [44]. Karakitapoğlu Aygün, Z., Arslan, M., & Güney, S. (2008). Work values of Turkish and American university students. *Journal of Business Ethics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-007-9413-5>
- [45]. Khuzaeni, K. (2013). The Influence of Work Culture, Work Stress to the Job Satisfaction and Employees Performance in the State Treasury Service Office in Jakarta, Indonesia. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*. <https://doi.org/10.9790/487x-0924954>
- [46]. Kimbal, R. W. (2015). The design of ideal social capital for the development of traditional market in the mix-barter transaction in pasar blante kawangkoan. *International Journal of Applied Business and Economic Research*.
- [47]. Kimbal, R. W., & Tangkau, J. E. (2021). Social Capital Values as the Strengthening Elements in the Rural Small Industry. *Journal of International Conference Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.32535/jicp.v4i1.1158>
- [48]. Kirkley, W. W. (2016). Entrepreneurial behaviour: the role of values. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEBR-02-2015-0042>
- [49]. Kjellman, A., & Ehrsten, M. (2005). A Theory of Homo Entrepreneurus. In *Research on Technological Innovation, Management and Policy*.

- [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0737-1071\(05\)09012-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0737-1071(05)09012-8)
- [50]. Kopren, A., & Westlund, H. (2021). Bridging versus bonding social capital in entrepreneurs' networks: The case of post-conflict western balkans. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13063371>
- [51]. Korneiko, O. (2017). Value Orientations of Modern Entrepreneurship in Russia. *Economic and Social Changes: Facts, Trends, Forecast / Экономические и Социальные Перемены: Факты, Тенденции, Прогноз*. <https://doi.org/10.15838/esc.2017.5.53.12>
- [52]. Kuratko, D. F., Morris, M. H., & Schindehutte, M. (2015). Understanding the dynamics of entrepreneurship through framework approaches. *Small Business Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-015-9627-3>
- [53]. Kuron, L. K. J., Lyons, S. T., Schweitzer, L., & Ng, E. S. W. (2015). Millennials' work values: differences across the school to work transition. *Personnel Review*, 44(6), 991–1009. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-01-2014-0024>
- [54]. Kyndt, E., & Baert, H. (2015). Entrepreneurial competencies: Assessment and predictive value for entrepreneurship. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2015.07.002>
- [55]. Laspita, S., Breugst, N., Heblich, S., & Patzelt, H. (2012). Intergenerational transmission of entrepreneurial intentions. *Journal of Business Venturing*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusvent.2011.11.006>
- [56]. Leuty, M. E., & Hansen, J. I. C. (2011). Evidence of construct validity for work values. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2011.04.008>
- [57]. Malebana, M. J. (2019). The influencing role of social capital in the formation of entrepreneurial intention. *Southern African Business Review*. <https://doi.org/10.25159/1998-8125/6043>
- [58]. Malinowska, D., & Tokarz, A. (2019). Workaholism Components in Relation to Life and Work Values. *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11469-019-00089-y>
- [59]. McClelland, D. C., & McClelland, D. C. (2013). Entrepreneurial behavior. In *The achieving society*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/14359-006>
- [60]. Miquel, G. P. i, Qian, N., Xu, Y., & Yao, Y. (2015). Making Democracy Work: Culture, Social Capital and Elections in China. *National Bureau of Economic Research*. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w21058>
- [61]. Mueller, S. L., & Thomas, A. S. (2001). Culture and entrepreneurial potential: A nine country study of locus of control and innovativeness. *Journal of Business Venturing*. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026\(99\)00039-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026(99)00039-7)
- [62]. Nahapiet, J., & Ghoshal, S. (2009). Social capital, intellectual capital, and the organizational advantage. In *Knowledge and Social Capital*. <https://doi.org/10.2307/259373>
- [63]. Nursiani, N. P., Fanggidae, R. E., Fanggidae, R. P. ., & Messakh, S. (2019). Spirituality and Entrepreneurs: Analysis of Entrepreneurial Motivation. *GATR Journal of Management and Marketing Review*. [https://doi.org/10.35609/jmmr.2019.4.1\(8\)](https://doi.org/10.35609/jmmr.2019.4.1(8))
- [64]. Oles, P. K., & Hermans, H. J. M. (2010). Allport-Vernon Study of Values. In *The Corsini Encyclopedia of Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470479216.corpsy0038>
- [65]. Parry, E., & Urwin, P. (2011). Generational Differences in Work Values: A Review of Theory and Evidence. In *International Journal of Management Reviews*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2370.2010.00285.x>
- [66]. Portes, A. (2009). Social capital: Its origins and applications in modern sociology. In *Knowledge and Social Capital*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-7506-7222-1.50006-4>
- [67]. Raitis, J., Sasaki, I., & Kotlar, J. (2021). System-Spanning Values Work and Entrepreneurial Growth in Family Firms. *Journal of Management Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joms.12653>
- [68]. Ramdhani, S. (2020). Pengembangan Ekonomi Kreatif dan Keragaman Budaya dalam Perspektif Antropologi. *Empower: Jurnal Pengembangan Masyarakat Islam*. <https://doi.org/10.24235/empower.v5i1.6300>
- [69]. Robbins, Stephen P., & Judge, T. A. (2017). Organizational Behavior (17th) Edition. *Pearson Education Limited*.
- [70]. Rokeach, M. (1973). Understanding Human Values. *The Nature of Human Values*.
- [71]. Ros, M., Schwartz, S. H., & Surkiss, S. (1999). Basic individual values, work values, and the meaning of work. *Applied Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/026999499377664>
- [72]. Sahut, J. M., & Peris-Ortiz, M. (2014). Small business, innovation, and entrepreneurship. *Small Business Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-013-9521-9>
- [73]. Sánchez, A. C. (2021). Personal values as predictors of entrepreneurial intentions of university students. *Journal of Evolutionary Studies in Business*. <https://doi.org/10.1344/jesb2021.2.j096>
- [74]. Schouten, M. (n.d.). *Old and New Élite in a Village of Sonder*.
- [75]. Schouten, Maria J. (2004). Manifold connections: The Minahasa region in Indonesia. *South East Asia Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5367/0000000041524699>
- [76]. Schouten, Maria Johanna. (2019). *Schouten , Mieke (Maria Johanna) Eras and areas : export crops and subsistence in Minahasa , 1817-1985 , First Conference of the European Association for South-East Asian Studies . Pane ... June 1995*.
- [77]. Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). Research Method for Business Textbook: A Skill Building Approach. *John Wiley & Sons Ltd*.
- [78]. Senik, C., & Verdier, T. (2011). Segregation, entrepreneurship and work values: The case of France. *Journal of Population Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00148-010-0328-6>
- [79]. Singarimbun, M. (2006). sofian Effendi. In *Metode Penelitian Survei*.
- [80]. Sinha, S., Singh, A. K., Gupta, N., & Dutt, R. (2010). Impact of Work Culture on Motivation and Performance Level of Employees in Private Sector Companies. *Acta Oeconomica Pragensia*. <https://doi.org/10.18267/j.aop.321>

- [81]. Soininen, J., Puumalainen, K., Sjögrén, H., Syrjä, P., & Richter, C. (2015). What drives entrepreneurial orientation in small firms? The roles of owner-manager and financial conditions. *International Journal of Business Excellence*.
<https://doi.org/10.1504/IJBEX.2015.065981>
- [82]. Sugiyono. (2016). Sugiyono, Metode Penelitian. *Sugiyono*.
- [83]. Suharsimi, A. (2002). Metodologi Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Proposal. In 2017.
- [84]. Supranto. (2001). Pengukuran Tingkat Kepuasan Pelanggan Untuk Meningkatkan Pangsa Pasar. *Jakarta, Rineka Cipta*.
- [85]. Terrell, K., & Troilo, M. (2010). Values and female entrepreneurship. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/17566261011079242>
- [86]. Tipu, S. A. A., & Ryan, J. C. (2016). Predicting entrepreneurial intentions from work values: Implications for stimulating entrepreneurship in UAE national youth. *Management Decision*.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-09-2015-0387>
- [87]. Torres, P., & Augusto, M. (2019). Cultural configurations and entrepreneurial realisation. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEER-12-2017-0525>
- [88]. Twenge, J. M., Campbell, S. M., Hoffman, B. J., & Lance, C. E. (2010). Generational differences in work values: Leisure and extrinsic values increasing, social and intrinsic values decreasing. *Journal of Management*.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206309352246>
- [89]. Vuorio, A. M., Puumalainen, K., & Fellnhöfer, K. (2018). Drivers of entrepreneurial intentions in sustainable entrepreneurship. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research*.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEER-03-2016-0097>
- [90]. Wenas, J. (n.d.). *Sejarah dan kebudayaan {Minahasa} - {Jessy} {Wenas} - {2007} {Buku}*.
- [91]. Whiteley, P. F. (2015). Social Capital. In *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences: Second Edition*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-097086-8.93127-1>
- [92]. Wyrwich, M. (2015). Entrepreneurship and the intergenerational transmission of values. *Small Business Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-015-9649-x>
- [93]. Zhang, H., Han, R., Wang, L., & Lin, R. (2021). Social capital in China: a systematic literature review. *Asian Business and Management*.
<https://doi.org/10.1057/s41291-019-00081-3>